

STUDYING THE TOPIC “FEATURES OF MANAGING UNITS IN VARIOUS TYPES OF COMBAT” USING INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7631718>

Abstract. *This article discusses the accessibility, benefits and prospects of using interactive technologies for studying the discipline "Tactics of common military combat" and what it consists of.*

Keywords: *combat, tactics, armament, cadet, method.*

INTRODUCTION

In the education system considerable attention has recently paid to improving, systematizing, as well as optimizing the processes of obtaining theoretical knowledge and practical skills by students in military educational institutions such as the Military Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, military faculties, military departments. Today, studying in the higher education system provides good opportunities for young professionals to start building a career, having behind them an extensive baggage of knowledge and skills that are necessary for their future professional activity. Highly qualified workers and top-level specialists are currently in great demand on the labor exchange in a variety of areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When studying the tactics of conducting common military combat, it is necessary to acquire skills such as firmness in decision-making, correct assessment of the situation and its general vision, understanding where, how and what is more profitable to perform combat tasks, train endurance and join the staff culture. In the absence of proper imagination and knowledge, it will be difficult to comprehend the art of conducting common military combat. That is why the role of innovative technologies in the troops is rapidly increasing both for the training of commanders and their personnel, and for their conduct of combat. Innovative technologies make it possible to train specialists more efficiently, provide flexibility in the educational process, which makes it possible to make adjustments to it depending on objectively changing requirements for a specialist.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of new information technologies in the educational process, which should be aimed at the development of abilities and intellectual and creative potential, coherence, as well as confidence in actions, will bring great benefits in the development of abilities and intellectual and creative potential, coherence, and confidence in actions [1]:

- creation of virtual simulators;
- creation of training (demonstration) programs;
- creation of electronic textbooks;

- creation of testing programs;
- creation of electronic educational and methodical complexes.

It is possible to evaluate the quality of the developed training programs according to two groups of criteria: according to methodological, according to technological. The technological makes it possible to determine the flexibility, simplicity and accessibility of the content of educational material. The methodological evaluates the complexity of this material, as well as the presence of stages in the formation of competence: presentation, demonstration, consolidation and verification of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

The development of training programs should be implemented based on a scientific approach, taking into account the continuously increasing requirements for the competence of young specialists, as well as for optimizing the training process itself. In the course of drawing up a training program for specialists, time is allotted for both theoretical and practical interrelated classes, as well as exercises and tactical-special classes. At the theoretical lessons, the most relevant information is given, which is subsequently worked out in practical classes, and during the exercises, in addition, interaction with other departments. The training program must meet the following criteria: the presence of a structural-logical connection and the optimal sequence in the study of educational materials within the topics of classes, adherence to the principle of combination.

Optimization of the training program for military specialists should be carried out in at least three areas: the first is the continuous improvement of the content of educational materials, the second is the development and implementation of new forms and methods of training that provide the opportunity in the shortest possible time and at the lowest cost to achieve the highest possible results in the training of specialists, the third is to have a high-quality and simple approach to bringing educational material and the transfer of existing experience by teachers to students, to know and bring to students what is the importance of the subject being studied. The better and more accessible the teachers will conduct their classes, the better the learning material will be assimilated by the students.

It is possible to evaluate the quality of the developed training programs according to two groups of criteria: methodological and technological. The technological makes it possible to determine the flexibility, simplicity and accessibility of the content of educational material. The methodological evaluates the complexity of this material, as well as the presence of stages of formation of competence: presentation, demonstration, consolidation and control of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

Currently, the following shooting simulators are used in the armed forces of the CIS countries: «СКАТТ», «АРГОН», «РУБИН», «Тир», 1У33-Ижмаш [2].

The simulators use 3D graphics, which makes the panoramic image very realistic and dynamic. But the program of the simulator has only 6 scenarios, does not allow the head of the lesson to independently change the conditions for performing the exercise, there is no visualization of the actions of the student, which makes the use of this simulator in teaching shooting ineffective.

Simulators provide an opportunity to train cadets on [3]:

- 1)performing shooting practice exercises,
- 2)the correctness of the report in the course of their implementation,
- 3)train cadets in the correct way of giving commands by the commander when controlling the fire of the unit.

CONCLUSION

At the moment, innovative technologies will not fully replace classes in fields or on landfills, but they will allow a more comprehensive study of the theoretical basis of various disciplines, as well as help to better optimize the educational process and increase its informativeness and ease of assimilation of educational material in general.

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